

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF FAIRY TALES IN A CHILD'S LIFE. THE ROLE OF FOLK TALES IN THE DEVELOPMENT AND UPBRINGING OF CHILDREN. AT THE SAME TIME, THE IMPORTANCE OF IT IN LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE. ITS ROLE IN INCREASING CREATIVITY.

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Abstract. *In modern pedagogical practice, traditional fairy tales play a vital role in teaching and learning any foreign languages. The fairy tale helps to form the basis of behavior and communication. The role of children's fairy tales is to develop the child's fantasy and imagination, as well as his creative potential. A fairy tale enters a child's life from a very early age, accompanies him throughout preschool childhood and remains with him for life. fairy tales carry centuries-old folk wisdom. They are very accessible and intelligibly explain to children certain aspects of human life, separate good from evil. That is why fairy tales are an integral part of children's education. Furthermore, the fairy tales make the learning process more interesting and regaled for young children.*

Key words: *preschool children, methods, folk tales, learning process, creativity, development of children.*

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ СКАЗКИ В ЖИЗНИ РЕБЕНКА. РОЛЬ НАРОДНЫХ СКАЗОК В РАЗВИТИИ И ВОСПИТАНИИ ДЕТЕЙ. В ТО ЖЕ ВРЕМЯ ПОДЧЕРКИВАЕТСЯ ВАЖНОСТЬ ЭТОГО В ИЗУЧЕНИИ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА. ЕГО РОЛЬ В ПОВЫШЕНИИ ТВОРЧЕСКОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА.

Аннотация. *В современной педагогической практике традиционные сказки играют важнейшую роль в преподавании и изучении любых иностранных языков. Сказка помогает сформировать основу поведения и общения. Роль детских сказок заключается в развитии фантазии и воображения ребенка, а также его творческого потенциала. Сказка входит в жизнь ребенка с самого раннего возраста, сопровождает его на протяжении всего дошкольного детства и остается с ним на всю жизнь. сказки несут в себе многовековую народную мудрость. Они очень доступно и доходчиво объясняют детям отдельные стороны человеческой жизни, отделяют добро от зла. Именно поэтому сказки являются неотъемлемой частью воспитания детей. Кроме того, сказки делают процесс обучения более интересным и увлекательным для маленьких детей.*

Ключевые слова: *дошкольники, методика, народные сказки, процесс обучения, творчество, развитие детей.*

A fairy tale - how much magic of kindness lies in this word. The child gets acquainted with the magical world of fairy tales at a very early age. And undoubtedly a fairy tale is a necessary stage in the mental development of a child. "Through a fairy tale, fantasy, game, through a unique children's creativity - the right way to the heart of a child. A fairy tale, fantasy is the key with which you can open these sources, and they will fill with life-giving keys," wrote V. Sukhomlinsky. A fairy tale is one of the available means for developing a child's emotions, relationships with the whole world around him. The world of fairy tales is a world of dreams and

fantasy. Do not deprive your baby of this magical world, because with faith in miracles, you can easily overcome all difficulties. Read fairy tales to children, think together about the actions of heroes, invent your own fairy tales - and this will undoubtedly be the best "simulator" in shaping your child's personality. Acquaintance with a fairy tale helps the child to understand the surrounding reality. Any fairy tale is a story about relationships between people. The child does not like instructions, and the fairy tale does not teach him directly. A children's fairy tale offers the child images that are very interesting to him. The role of children's fairy tales in the development of children is multifaceted.

From the development of fantasy to the development of correct speech. A fairy tale is an integral element in the education of children. She teaches children about life in an accessible language, talks about good and evil. Children understand a fairy tale more easily than insipid adult speech. Therefore, if adults want to help explain something to a child, support him, they will have to remember the language of childhood - a fairy tale. Reading and telling fairy tales, adults develop the inner world of the child. Children who read fairy tales from early childhood begin to speak faster, to express their thoughts correctly. Children's fairy tales expand the baby's vocabulary, help to build a dialogue correctly, develop coherent logical speech. It is equally important to make the child's speech emotional, beautiful, figurative. Developing the ability to ask questions. Great importance should be given to the construction of words, sentences, phrases. The connection between the speech and mental activity of children is very important. The fairy tale helps to form the basis of behavior and communication.

The role of children's fairy tales is to develop the fantasy and imagination of the child, as well as his creative potential. To read fairy tales, it is important to choose the "right" time when the child is calm and in a good mood. You can do this before going to bed when you have time to discuss the story. You need to read with pleasure and not be distracted, this will bring more benefits and positive emotions. Fairy tales expand the knowledge of children.

The story is a beautiful work of art. The child enters the world of fairy tales at a very early age, as soon as he begins to speak. There is a fairy tale in every home and enjoys great love among children. Children learn a lot from fairy tales. Thanks to fairy tales, children develop the ability to empathize, compassion and rejoice for another, this is the only way to know the pain, joy, happiness and suffering of another person. And it is fairy tales that bring up humanity in a child - a marvelous ability to sympathize with other people's misfortunes. The most amazing events, extraordinary transformations are common in a fairy tale. The perception of the world around young children is diverse. Children treat inanimate objects as they treat animate objects, and vice versa, treat animate objects as if they were inanimate. In this special world, the child easily and simply masters the connections of phenomena, masters a large stock of knowledge.

Folk art is the oldest art of humanity. Oral artistic creativity, which is a rare heritage of our national treasure, created by the Uzbek people for thousands of years, always serves as spiritual food for human perfection, country's well-being, and society's maturity. Folklore genres passed down safely from generation to generation serve as guides in social-political, educational-educational fields, schools, spiritual-educational direction. It is no exaggeration to say that proverbs and sayings, which have been proven as a result of people's life experiences and daily observations, are the textbooks of the school of life.

One of the reasons why the fairy tale genre is well accepted and read by children in folklore is the impressiveness, sharpness, meaning and closeness of the language of fairy tales. In most of the fairy tales, the depiction of real life is combined with elements of adventure. The sharp, interesting subject of the fairy tale, the extraordinarily wonderful situation in the development of the story will fascinate children, the brave, strong, resourceful, brave, agile heroes, the ideological direction of the fairy tale, the constant victory of the power of goodness in it will attract children. pulls The form of storytelling adopted in a fairy tale is repetition of the same words and phrases over and over again, melodiousness, impressiveness of the language, vividness of the means of expression, very interesting for children. The participants in fairy tales are often the personification of compassionate, generous, fair and their opposite, evil, miserly, greedy people. The pedagogical value of the fairy tale is that the students are happy that the truth and honesty won in it, that the poor people got out of trouble, that is, that goodness and goodness came true, and that evil and wickedness were condemned.

They always want it to be like this in life. For example, in the tale "Honesty" (12.30) the main idea is to help the poor, to live by one's own work, and the idea that this is even the desire of the whole nation is put forward, in the tale "The Punishment of the Trickster" and (8.57) the idea that the truth of the simple-minded will win over the tricks of the trickster, and that betrayal will not go unpunished, is put forward. Both tales end with the victory of righteousness. Animal stories are taught more often in elementary grades. Fairy tales such as "The tale of the wolf as a doctor" (A. Obidjon) (8.70), "The fox with the jug" (8.51) are taught and analyzed in the style of real life stories. When working on the text of a fairy tale, the following types of work are used: selective reading, answering questions, making up and answering questions about the content of the fairy tale, making a plan, retelling, creative continuation, telling a story, graphically depicting the characters. In such tales, the habits of animals are analyzed, but it is not recommended to compare them with the character of people. It is known from school experience that young students know well that animals in fairy tales do not speak, foxes and cranes do not visit each other, but they perceive the world of fairy tales as a real life story.

When reading and analyzing a fairy tale, all work is directed to a better understanding of the content of the text, to correctly imagine the development of the subject, the behavior of the participating characters, and their interactions. Selective reading and retelling are important in this. For example, the following tasks can be used to master the content of the fairy tale "Is it easy to be polite?" (A. Obidjon) (8.113): 1. Read the mouse's conversation with his mother. Describe how the mother responded to the mouse's question, "What do you need to do to be polite?" 2. Find and read the scene where the mouse meets the cat. Why does the evil in Shum Barak's eyes disappear suddenly? 3. Why does the Goat pray to the Mouse "Don't be short"? Find this place and read it. At the final stage of the analysis of the fairy tale, the students' summary of the fairy tale is made using questions such as "Find and read the part of the fairy tale that you really liked", "Tell me why you liked this particular part", "Have there been any events in your life similar to the events in the fairy tale?" understanding is achieved. In addition to fairy tales about animals, elementary school students read "The State" (4-p.49-b), "Ilm Afzal" (4-p.44-b), "The Trickster's Punishment" (4-p.57- b), they also read folk tales such as "A person without skills is close to death" (4-s.61-b). In such fairy tales, the people tell their lives, therefore, after reading the fairy tale, the students will

learn about the life of the people in the past, their thoughts and dreams. The analysis of such tales is organized in the style of an artistic story.

Under the guidance of the teacher, children evaluate the behavior and certain actions of the participants in the fairy tale, tell their relationship to each other and draw conclusions about some characters on the basis of these, draw up a plan of the fairy tale, read the fairy tale in roles. "State" A fairy tale is a fairy tale that describes events related to ordinary life. To prepare for reading the fairy tale, a conversation is held about how our ancestors imagined the nature and existence around us. Such a conversation helps to understand the artistic characters in the fairy tale, their mutual relations, behavior, and characters. In the process of working on the text of the fairy tale "The State", students evaluate the heroes of the tale by finding answers to questions such as "How does the peasant's household live?", "Why does the State not want to leave the peasant's household?" they come to the conclusion that it is necessary. When working on a fairy tale, it is important to teach children not only to read a fairy tale, but also to tell it. Telling stories develops oral speech, enriches children's speech with new words and phrases. In order to teach students to use the language of fairy tales freely in the 1st grade, the teacher can tell it during the first introduction to the fairy tale. After the student has mastered the content of the fairy tale, it is necessary to pay special attention to working on his language. When retelling the content of the fairy tale, describing the characters, students are required to use language tools appropriately in their own speech.

It is necessary to create a demand and a situation, a need for using language tools. There are words and phrases in fairy tale language that have a special effect on a child. For example, in the fairy tale "Tiger, Fox and Wolf" "May the mountain goat be our great one", "May the hare be our king's morning breakfast", "Deer be your evening meal, sheep your midday meal" It is necessary to pay attention to the highlighted words in sentences such as "let's be" and use them in speech while telling the story. It is necessary to work on the proverbs presented in the fairy tales, to convey the ideas presented in them to the minds of children, to develop communicative speech through memorization, and to increase the effectiveness of the speech. For example, in the fairy tale "Honest Boy" it is told that the boy liked the king with his honesty. This fairy tale should be passed on the basis of new pedagogical technology. Information about the genres of fairy tales and anecdotes, which have an important place in the science of folklore. Elucidate the role of fairy tales and anecdotes in folklore, their language and artistic features. Demonstration of educational tools, scientific research works, pamphlets and monographs of folklorists on fairy tales to students. It is appropriate to use blitz surveys, traditional lectures, interviews, and short tests

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